

A pump with a PVC tubewell (estimated cost: US\$188) could replace more expensive shallow tubewells. The cost of irrigation is about 3.5 times less (Table 2). The pump also saves the 350 liters of diesel per hectare required by shallow, engine driven tubewells.

The pump is dependable and uses inexpensive fabrication materials available, even in remote areas. ☺

Table 2. Irrigation costs of BRRRI animal-driven pump and engine-operated shallow tubewell.

Equipment	Av measured discharge (liter/s)	Irrigation requirement (m ³ /ha)	Total pumping period (h/ha)	Total cost of irrigation (US \$/ha)	Command area (ha/season, rice)
BRRRI animal-driven pump	2.8	10,000	980	27.8	1.2
Shallow tubewell	12.0	10,000	232	103.0	4.9

Inverted-T multicrop seeder for rice-based cropping systems

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A new multicrop seeder utilizes a mechanical design developed on the basis of soil physical requirements for improved seed germination and seedling emergence.

The seeder (see figure) incorporates an inverted-T opener, which creates seed microenvironments tolerant of a wide range of field conditions in both previously tilled and untilled soil conditions. The subsurface soil shattering created by the inverted-T seeder facilitates shoot and root proliferation and improves in-grove moisture availability.

A depth wheel ensures proper seed depth. It also serves as a presswheel to provide seed cover and to improve seed-soil contact, enhancing moisture conductivity at the seed-soil interface. The wheel also drives the seed metering unit.

The seeder utilizes a seed metering assembly originally designed by Aitchison Industries, New Zealand, which provides a high degree of metering and delivery accuracy with minimum periodicity and no seed damage. Almost all crop seeds — maize, beans, rice, peanuts — can be

Inverted-T multicrop seeder. IRRI, 1986.

satisfactorily metered and sown. A horizontally mounted circular foam pad attached to a steel pad rotates along the vertical plate of the plastic hopper base. Seeds are delivered down through a throat-type opening mounted on the hopper base. The galvanized sheet iron hopper is attached directly over the plastic base.

The single-row unit model can be

mounted on a two-wheel tractor for seeding in both previously tilled and untilled upland and lowland soils. A simple and easily attached drag arm in front of the seeder allows it to be operated by animals.

Production cost of the seeder, manufactured by small metalworking shops, is estimated to be less than US\$100. ☺

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